

**INFLUENCE OF PERSONAL AND ORGANISATIONAL FACTORS ON THE USE OF
MOBILE APPLICATIONS FOR PROMOTING UNIVERSITY LAW LIBRARY SERVICES IN
SOUTH-WEST, NIGERIA DURING COVID-19 PANDMIC**

OLUDAYO JOHN BAMGBOSE,

Ajayi Crowther University, Oyo, Nigeria.

oj.bamgbose@acu.edu.ng

and

DAPO-ASAJU, HARRIET SEUN

Lagos State University, Nigeria

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ABSTRACT

The study population comprised of personnel of university law libraries in all accredited nineteen universities offering law at undergraduate level in South-west, Nigeria. Using Media Richness Theory as theoretical framework, descriptive survey design of correlational type was adopted for the study. Out of the 107 copies of the questionnaire administered, 97 were validly completed, returned and used for the analysis. The findings from the study revealed positive significant relationships between use of mobile applications for promotion of law library services and age of respondents and years of work experience. Meanwhile, there were no significant relationship between use of mobile applications for promotion of law library services and library policy, ICT skills, adequacy of funding, environmental factors and infrastructure. It also shows the joint contribution of personal factors (gender, age, status, position, academic qualification, years of work experience and section of the library) on the use of mobile applications for promotion of law library services in South-West, Nigeria. The study shows that personal factors particularly influence the use of mobile application for the promotion of law library services. It is recommended that there is awareness and capacity building among staff of law libraries on the use of mobile applications in promoting law library services.

Keywords: Personal factors, Organisational factors, Mobile applications, Promotional services, University law libraries in South-west

Introduction

From the discovery of the Covid-19 in Wuhan to the mutation of its delta variant and the emergence of omicron in South Africa, there has been an increasing need to deploy the use of mobile app. as well as other mobile hand-held and other technological devices in the marketing of library services to clientele and patrons due to the inability of patrons to physically visit the law library. Meanwhile, the study and practice of law are largely library-based (Owushi and Anyalebech, 2025). The law library is a centre where users, including: students, faculty, law school staff, attorneys, jurists and the general public are guaranteed access to legal information resources (Runyon, 2013). In recognition of its importance to the advancement of legal education and the administration of justice, the law library has been described ‘heart of the law school’ (Dapo-Asaju, 2017). In view of this, the law library has become an essential component in legal education in Nigeria. Suffice to state however that lately, observation has shown that the patronage of the traditional law library by the law students is gradually declining by the day. Monali (2014) noted that the decline in the use of traditional law library can be attributed to the availability of electronic resources which

students and researchers can now explore in the place of print resources.

Council of Legal Education (CLE), Nigeria mandates institutions desirous of mounting the study of law to demonstrate the institution’s capacity to provide e-resources for the use of its patrons before such institution could be accredited for the study of law in Nigeria (Council of Legal Education, 2013). Actually, deployment of electronic-based resources also guarantees that access to resources is provided to patrons beyond the typical eight-hours-working-period in the traditional print library system. It should be noted that hitherto, the law library confined its services to that which could only enhance reading and research endeavours of its clients. In achieving this, personnel with requisite broad skills that could actualise these objectives were employed by the law library. However, as time went by, it became apparent that the calling of law librarians would transcend mere provision of information to users and the training of budding lawyers (Bamgbose, 2016; Lala and Okuonghae, 2022). In the same vein, it has also been reported that there is a gradual paradigm shift in the demographic statistics of users of the law library. Unlike before, there is now a rise in

the number of non-lawyers visiting the law library for the purpose of searching for information (Zorza, 2012). This can be attributed to numerous factors such as the difficulty in accessing legal aid and other *pro bono* (free legal support from lawyers) related services.

With increase in the preference for electronic legal information, law librarians now strive to ensure that they are able to leverage on the availability of Information and Communication Technologies (ICTs) in the discharge of their duties. The emergence of smart phones has resulted in greater interactions online using these devices. While, mobile app is highly recommended for research, it has been suggested that caution must also be exercised to protect users from hackers who may easily access the cached user information, thereby constituting an act of security breach (Sharma, 2017). At present, the youths spend more time on the phone, the Internet or in front of the television screen. The mobile phone usage pattern of youths has become worrisome because most of them use their phones excessively (Mamuda, 2015). This is in agreement with the position of Kalyani (2024) technology has copious benefits in

meeting the information needs of clientele of the law library.

Despite the perceived likelihood of security breach, smartphones and mobile application now play crucial role in communication in the modern day. Nielson (2014) observed that mobile apps have now become an integral part of the daily lives of people such that people now spend an average of 30 hours on monthly basis in carrying out app-based activities. Nielson further found out that Android and iPhone users aged 18 years spent more than 65% of their time using apps each month in the year 2011. Mobile app users within the age bracket 18-24 years spent the most time on apps which was 37 hours, 6 minutes per month. This is in agreement with the submission of Tiongson (2015) that people actually download apps every day. It may be safe, therefore, to predict that judging from the use of mobile apps, the increasing installations and number of viewers, the attention and time given to mobile app programme will increase in the future.

In Nigeria, Non-Governmental Organisations (NGOs), banks and few other financial institutions, such as pension managers and insurance outfits now have mobile apps which their customers can use for easy and

quick financial transactions. Its use is most popular particularly, among the youth (Ozonuwe, Ayomide and Ohwofasa, 2021; Babatunde *et al*, 2025). Little wonder then that Beniwal and Sharma (2013) opined that the use of mobile phones has affected the youth to a large extent and, therefore dependency on mobile phones is increasing day by day. However, the use of mobile applications has not been well maximised by educational institutions in Nigeria, particularly, the law libraries. The reason for this may be attributed to the challenge of not having adequately trained personnel that could develop these applications. In some instances, the personnel are constrained by lack of facilities to develop and further manage of the apps effectively.

It is against this background that this study is interested in examining what role the adoption of mobile app. technology can play in the promotion of law library services. Essentially, promotion is the means of informing users on what you do and what you can do (Akorhonor, 2005). The use of mobile phones has become the order of the day, and as such, its use can be leveraged upon to achieve promotional services in the law libraries. Commenting on the role of mobile phones in the contemporary society,

Abdulrahman, Soetan, Onojah and Aderoju (2024) asserted that the use of mobile/cell phones has really improved academic challenges in recent times. Basi (2009) further emphasised that the academic environment is moving into a paperless society and that any student who does not use the Internet often should use their cell phones to generate information to meet their academic pursuit, or such students would be left behind, because ICT is a moving train. Promotion of library services and activities take the form of marketing. Essentially, libraries engage in marketing in order to promote the use of available reading material in the library and create awareness among the users; optimise the use of information within limited resources and manpower; raise internally generated revenue that could complement the limited resources; and improve the image of the library (Patil and Tadasad, 2015). Ways through which libraries promote their services include organisation of information literacy programme on regular basis at various levels; organisation of educational programmes and activities such as workshops/ training programmes about awareness of resources available in the libraries and Information centres; facilitation of in-house training

programmes for library staff using expert facilitators with cognate experience; mounting of exhibitions of new books with the help of vendors and/ or the material available in the library should be displayed at prominent place (Patil and Tadasad, 2015).

The influence of personal factors on staff to work has been well researched. This is because of its impact on the quality of work of personnel. Popoola (2012), while enumerating the personal factors which enhance job satisfaction, maintained that gender, age, education, marital status, job tenure and income could, to a large extent, determine a worker's level of efficiency, and then, satisfaction. Other personal factors could include the number of dependents of the worker, years of service, intelligent quotient, education and non-intellectual personality (Adeeko, Basiru and Akintola, 2023). Organisational factors also affect staff performances at work. Unlike the personal factors which an organisation could have little influence on, organisational factors are largely within the domain of the management of an organisation who formulate and implement policies. Some of the factors that constitute organisational factors may range from remuneration, access to on-the-job training, support for personal development,

awards and promotions. Staff respond to the organisational culture and where the management make it as a point of duty to create a favourable climate for staff to operate. Such may serve as a motivating factor for them to put their best into the services of the organisation. Such culture has a tendency of imbuing in the staff, the mentality of having a stake in the activities of the said organisation.

Statement of the problem

As important as the use of the law library is, it has been regrettably observed that the patronage of the physical and electronic collections of the law library in the recent times is decreasing despite the increase in the budget to the law library and the enrolment of students and staff of law faculties in Nigeria. Simply put, the level of usage of the resources does not justify the investments made in the university law libraries in Nigeria. Similarly, with the coming of covid-19 into the global space, the need to adopt new and emerging technologies such as the use of mobile application for marketing of law library services cannot be over emphasised in the era of Covid-19 where physical interaction has been limited. A further and careful observation of the pattern of usage of legal resources in the law

library have revealed that personal factors (age, gender, level of education, experience, marital status, job tenure and income) have influence on the individuals' use of mobile application for the promotion of library services. In the same vein, organisational factors (policy, infrastructure, environment, ICT skills and funding) could enhance the personal use of mobile applications for the promotion of library services. Based on the available and limited information at the disposal of the researchers, there seems to be a dearth of literature to empirically justify how personal and organisational factors influence the use of mobile application in the promotion of library services among law librarians in universities in Nigeria and so there is the need to fill the knowledge gap. This study, therefore, determines the relationship between personal and organisational factors and the personal use of mobile applications for promoting library services in law libraries in South-west, Nigeria.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The descriptive survey design of correlational type was adopted for this study while the population of the study comprised universities that mount the study of law at undergraduate level in Oyo, Osun, Ogun,

Ondo, Ekiti and Lagos States of South-west, Nigeria. The states share similar culture, ethnic nationality, and common history and have the earliest universities in Nigeria. Nineteen (19) federal, states and private universities made up the study. Total enumeration sampling technique was adopted for this study, therefore, the entire personnel in all the law libraries in the South-west, Nigeria took part in the study. The choice of total enumeration is in agreement with the submissions of Isangedighi and Ogomaka (1992) and Denscombe (2003) that where the population size of a study is sizeable, the entire population could to be studied.

The entire members of staff were chosen because they often play complementary roles due to constraint of sufficient personnel in the law library. The research instrument for this study is questionnaire. Questionnaire was designed to elicit information from librarians on the personal and organisational factors that influence the use of mobile application for the promotion of library services in the law libraries in South-west, Nigeria. The questionnaire was tagged Librarians' Personal and Organisation Factors for Mobile Application Promotional Service Delivery

Questionnaire (LPOFMAPSDQ) and structured into sections (A, B, C, D, E and F) with scale to measure the constructs in the research. To ensure the face and content validity of the research instrument, a copy of the questionnaire was provided to the professionals and lecturers in the Department of Library, Archival and Information Studies, University of Ibadan for their inputs. The responses elicited from this process were improved upon. Thereafter, a pre-test of the questionnaire was administered on 20 law library personnel outside the study zone so as to ensure that the reliability coefficient of the items of the research instrument (questionnaire) using Cronbach Alpha. The data obtained was used to test the reliability co-efficient of the questionnaire.

A total number of 107 copies of the questionnaire were distributed, however, 97 copies were returned and found useful for analysis, giving a response rate of 90.6%. The data generated from the study was analysed using descriptive and inferential statistics which included frequency counts, percentages, mean and standard deviation for the research questions. Correlation analysis and regression analysis were adopted for the research hypotheses. Multiple regression analysis and Pearson's product moment

correlation were used to test the hypotheses for the study at 0.05 level of significance. The quantitative data were analysed using Statistical Package for Social Sciences.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Research question one: what are the personal factors affecting the use of mobile applications for promoting library services in university law libraries in South-west, Nigeria during covid-19?

The study revealed that male respondents were more than the female respondents. This suggests there is male representation, in terms of the distribution of personnel to various units in the university law libraries in South-west, Nigeria. This is in agreement with a study by Elleus (1994) which stated that there is disproportionate male-female ratio in some professions and that this disproportionate distributions made it difficult for several women to interact well with their male colleagues. Although the findings showed that male respondents outnumbered the female respondents, it appears that there is hope that women will be given more responsibilities in the library with time. Ogunleye (2006) revealed that technology has increased women's

participation in both private and public sectors.

The studies also revealed that majority of the respondents were within the age group 25-33 years of age. This concurs with the study of Anumaka and Ssemugenyi (2013) that the age bracket of majority of workers in academic institutions now fall between 20 and 39 years. Majority of the library staff fall within the Librarian II cadre which connotes that majority of the library staff are relatively new in the system. Also, holders of Higher National Diploma (HND) and Bachelor of Library and Information Studies (BLIS) certificates constituted majority of the respondents with not more than five years working experience. From the foregoing, it can be deduced that the population is constituted largely by young persons. This seems to be beneficial to the study considering the fact that the subject of this study revolves round ICT. This is in

consonance with existing literature that younger staff of the library were proficient in the use of information technology. It also means that the population will require both academic and professional trainings to become more proficient in their daily routines. This is in conformity with Senyah's observation that no matter the size of library, as well as the scope and richness of the collection, the manager of a library cannot meet his set goals if the staff are not well-trained, properly equipped and highly motivated. The bulk of the respondents work at the readers' services section of the library, while those who work at the e-resources and digitization sections are very few. This suggests that the e-services rendered by the respondents is on the low side, or the staff from other units of the law library occasionally assist the e-library department in discharging some of its routines.

Research question two: What are the organisational factors affecting the use of mobile applications for promoting library services in university law libraries in South-West, Nigeria during covid-19 pandemic?

Research question two: What are the organizational factors affecting the use of mobile applications for promoting library services in university law libraries in South-West, Nigeria?

Table 2: Organizational factors affecting the use of mobile applications for promoting library services in university law libraries in South-West, Nigeria

s/n	Statement on types of mobile apps	1	2	3	4	\bar{x}	SD
1	The policy identifies staff with valuable tacit knowledge	9 9.3%	36 37.1%	35 36.1%	17 17.5%	2.62	0.88
2	Your library makes use of mobile application for the promotion of library services	14 14.4%	30 30.9%	34 35.1%	19 19.6%	2.60	0.96
3	The policy provides for job rotation of the library staff	10 10.3%	36 37.1%	37 38.1%	14 14.4%	2.57	0.86
4	The policy approves short courses in knowledge management for staff	13 13.4%	37 38.1%	33 34.0%	14 14.4%	2.49	0.90
5	The policy provides for formal training for library staff	13 13.4%	38 39.2%	39 40.2%	7 7.2%	2.41	0.81
6	The policy includes timely posting and updating of information	15 15.5%	39 40.2%	34 35.1%	9 9.3%	2.38	0.86
7	The policy extends to checks on copyright and other intellectual property matters	17 17.5%	37 38.1%	37 38.1%	6 6.2%	2.33	0.84
8	Social media use for service delivery is included in the policy	18 18.6%	46 47.4%	25 25.8%	8 8.2%	2.24	0.85
9	The mobile app policy of my law library has been reviewed at least, once since it was made	19 19.6%	45 46.4%	26 26.8%	7 7.2%	2.22	0.84
10	Privacy and other rights-based issues are included in the policy	20 20.6%	44 45.4%	28 28.9%	5 5.2%	2.19	0.82
11	Your library has written policy that guides the use of mobile application	17 17.5%	54 55.7%	19 19.6%	7 7.2%	2.16	0.80
12	The policy has provision for reviews when the need arises	20 20.6%	51 52.6%	17 17.5%	9 9.3%	2.15	0.86
13	The policy is published on the law library's websites	15 15.5%	58 59.8%	19 19.6%	5 5.2%	2.14	0.74
14	Your law library has a policy but it is unwritten	23 23.7%	50 51.5%	21 21.6%	3 3.1%	2.04	0.76
15	Your library has a written policy but I have never set my eyes on that policy	28 28.9%	54 55.7%	10 10.3%	5 5.2%	1.92	0.77
Weighted mean = 2.30							
s/n	Statement on types of mobile apps						
1	Mobile app development skill is necessary towards managing mobile apps	8 8.2%	17 17.5%	45 46.4%	27 27.8%	2.94	0.89
2	The use of Microsoft office is handy when it comes to managing mobile applications	4 4.1%	22 22.7%	49 50.5%	22 22.7%	2.92	0.79
3	Editing skills is highly essential in managing mobile applications in law libraries	9 9.3%	13 13.4%	55 56.7%	20 20.6%	2.89	0.84
4	The knowledge of protection of network /systems security against attacks and ethical hacking is import	4 4.1%	21 21.6%	55 56.7%	17 17.5%	2.88	0.74
5	The knowledge of database administration is generally essential	6 6.2%	21 21.6%	53 54.6%	17 17.5%	2.84	0.79

6	These services can actually be delegated or outsourced to consultants who can provide these services	13 13.4%	16 16.5%	42 43.3%	26 26.8%	2.84	0.98
7	Graphics designing is essential in managing mobile application	7 7.2%	23 23.7%	51 52.6%	16 16.5%	2.78	0.81
8	Software development skill is essential towards managing mobile apps	9 9.3%	29 29.9%	42 43.3%	17 17.5%	2.69	0.87
9	The library does not necessarily need to have all these skills to be able to function effectively	10 10.3%	23 23.7%	55 56.7%	9 9.3%	2.65	0.79
Weighted mean = 2.83							
s/n	Statements on Adequacy to funding						
1	There is adequate funding to support the mobile application project in my law library	8 8.2%	24 24.7%	40 41.2%	25 25.8%	2.85	0.91
2	With access to more funding, the law library can improve on the promotional services rendered through the use of mobile application in the library	11 11.3%	25 25.8%	38 39.2%	23 23.7%	2.75	0.95
3	We are constrained by lack of funds to support the mobile application project in the law library	11 11.3%	35 36.1%	27 27.8%	24 24.7%	2.66	0.98
4	There is provision in the current budget to the law library to maintain the mobile application	9 9.3%	40 41.2%	36 37.1%	12 12.4%	2.53	0.83
5	The support for the deployment of mobile application came ones and since then, there has not been provision to maintain this in the law library's budget	15 15.5%	37 38.1%	32 33.0%	13 13.4%	2.44	0.91
Weighted mean = 2.65							
s/n	Environmental factors						
1	There are functional air-conditioners in the law library	5 5.2%	27 27.8%	38 39.2%	27 27.8%	2.90	0.87
2	There is provision for lightening in the library	17 17.5%	12 12.4%	33 34.0%	35 36.1%	2.89	1.09
3	The office environment is conducive	13 13.4%	19 19.6%	37 38.1%	28 28.9%	2.82	1.00
4	The environmental factors affect the use of mobile applications	8 8.2%	27 27.8%	46 47.4%	16 16.5%	2.72	0.84
5	The weather condition is not conducive for the deployment of mobile application	8 8.2%	38 39.2%	36 37.1%	15 15.5%	2.60	0.85
6	Lack of proper ventilation and physical facilities affect the management of mobile application in the library	21 21.6%	23 23.7%	38 39.2%	15 15.5%	2.48	1.00
Weighted mean = 2.74							
Infrastructure							
Access to computers and phones							

1	There are computers and laptops for the promotional services in your law library	25 25.8%	7 7.2%	33 34.0%	32 33.0%	2.74	1.18
2	Antivirus software is installed on the devices to prevention computers and mobile devices corruption	19 19.6%	23 23.7%	29 29.9%	26 26.8%	2.64	1.08
3	The computers in your law library have genuine programmes and software	22 22.7%	15 15.5%	36 37.1%	24 24.7%	2.64	1.09
4	There are smart phones to enhance promotional services in your law library	20 20.6%	27 27.8%	30 30.9%	20 20.6%	2.52	1.04
5	There are enabling ICT facilities such as digital camera in your law library	20 20.6%	32 33.0%	24 24.7%	21 21.6%	2.47	1.05
Weighted mean = 2.60							
Access to Internet							
1	Internet connection to the law library is very fast and reliable	14 14.4%	16 16.5%	32 33.0%	35 36.1%	2.91	1.05
2	There is internet accessible in your law library	19 19.6%	14 14.4%	25 25.8%	39 40.2%	2.87	1.15
3	The internet bandwidth to the law library is of adequate quantity	18 18.6%	24 24.7%	30 30.9%	25 25.8%	2.64	1.06
4	I use my personal modem to access internet	28 28.9%	20 20.6%	30 30.9%	19 19.6%	2.41	1.11
5	There is provision for modem in the event of not having sufficient Internet access	22 22.7%	36 37.1%	26 26.8%	13 13.4%	2.31	0.97
Weighted mean = 2.63							
Availability of power supply							
1	There is availability of alternative sources of energy (Such as generators, inverter, Solar, Uninterruptable power supply, Power bank)	18 18.6%	10 10.3%	37 38.1%	32 33.0%	2.86	1.08
2	There is electricity supply in your law library	18 18.6%	15 15.5%	28 28.9%	36 37.1%	2.85	1.12
3	The electricity supply in the law library is from the grid (PHCN)	20 20.6%	18 18.6%	28 28.9%	31 32.0%	2.72	1.12
Weighted mean = 2.81							

The findings as reported in the Table 2 above shows that majority of the respondents were of the view that their law libraries had policies on the use of mobile applications in the promotion of law library services. Some respondents claimed that they the policy is

written and well publicised while some were of the view that although, their libraries had policies, but such policies were unwritten. Other respondents noted that there were no policies guarding the use of mobile applications for the promotion of law library

services in their law libraries. Suffice to state that the difference in the varying findings on the existence and publicity of library policy on the use of mobile applications may be attributed to the fact that not everyone may be aware of the existence of such policy, if it truly exists. Also, majority of the participants are staff within the junior staff category and may not be aware of existence of such policy, because policy issues are often discussed at the management level and except if well publicised, staff in junior category may be unaware of the existence of the policy.

On the content of the policy, the study revealed that the policy provided for job rotation of the library staff, short courses in knowledge management for staff and formal training for library staff. This implies, that the respondents, mainly, first degree holders have access to on-the-job training. The policy further includes timely posting and updating of information as well as provision for revision of the policy. The finding on the revision of the library policy is in consonance with the submission of Mokmin, Zawiyah and Nor (2012) that library policy has to be flexible if the library must continue to be relevant in the ever-changing world. The policy further extends to providing checks on the possibility of infringing on copyright and

other intellectual property matters. This is to help avert to avoidable litigations that the library may be subjected to if found to be in breach of the copyright law. There is also a provision for the use of social media in promoting law libraries services. Respondents further revealed that the policy addressed privacy and other rights-based issues that could be of concern to the users. One of such concerns could be cyberbullying. It was noted that the policy might have been reviewed at least once since it was made.

On the required ICT skills, respondents noted that mobile application development skill is necessary for managing mobile applications. This is corroborated by the findings of a previous study that mobile application skill is required for the proper management of mobile application platforms (Potnis, RegenstreifHarms and Cortez, 2016). Inukollu *et al* (2014) observed that many mobile application developers lack the needed the skills to develop functional skills. The skills on the use of Microsoft office in managing mobile applications is ranked next among the needed ICT skills. It was also revealed that editing skills is highly essential in managing mobile applications in law libraries while the knowledge of protection of network /systems security against attacks and ethical hacking is import is equally important. More so, the

knowledge of database administration, graphic designing and software development skills are very important in managing the mobile application. Meanwhile, some respondents are of the few that all the ICT skills are not important in managing the mobile application. It was stated that services associated with the management of the mobile application can be outsourced to persons to manage on behalf of the law library in question.

On the issue of funding, respondents were of the view that there is adequate funding to support mobile application projects in their law libraries. This finding is at variance with the submission of Ogunjimi, Bello and Olaniyi (2018) that libraries are generally underfunded. The finding also contradicts the observation of Igbokwe, Ezeji and Obidike (2010) that funding is the major challenge confronting marketing efforts of libraries in Nigeria. Anyaoku (2009) further asserted that constraint of fund has actually forced libraries to start collecting fees for services rendered to users. Komolafe-opadeji and Yacob (2012), while corroborating the reluctance of libraries to levy fees on the patrons, remarked that many academic libraries especially in Nigeria are actually uncomfortable pricing library services

rendered to their users. Ishola noted that the services that library users pay for included: registration fee, download fee, internet fee, data search fee, subscription fee, reservation fee and direct sales of publication. However, the respondents also noted that with access to more funding, the law library can improve on the promotional services rendered through the use of mobile application in the library. This later finding is supported by Igbokwe, Ezeji and Obidike (2010) who solicited for more funding in the library. This shows that access to funding can to a large extent, help the law library improve in their services to their clientele.

Environmentally, the study revealed that the law libraries have functional air-conditioners in the law library. This is support of Omeluzor (2017)'s observation that adequate infrastructure is requisite tool towards achieving the goals of university libraries in the 21st century. Similarly, Haliso (2011) further observed that inadequate library facility had hindered several library development projects. It is further revealed that there is provision for lightening in the library. This is agreement with the submission of Ojo, Subair and Olajide (2015) that lightening is very crucial to the management of library system. The

respondents also affirm that the office environment is conducive. Respondents also noted that environmental factors affect the use of mobile applications. However, it was also noted that the weather condition is not conducive for the deployment of mobile application and that lack of proper ventilation and physical facilities affect the management of mobile application in the library.

Findings revealed availability of computers and laptops for promotional services in the respective law libraries. This is agreement with the submission of Omeluzor, Nwosu and Molokwu (2018) that having the right infrastructure could help advance the services rendered in libraries. Akpoghome and Jerome (2010) also earlier noted that for law libraries to fully achieve their aims, they must be equipped with computers and other ICT materials. This is partly because much of legal research in the modern era are now conducted with the aid of computers and other ICT based facilities. Abubakar, Gupiyem and Mangud corroborated the need for libraries to be equipped with computers by averring that if the library must meet up with the 21st century demand of a modern library, computers must be provided to aid the teaching and learning services in the library.

Respondents were also of the view that antivirus software were installed on the devices to protect the computers and other mobile devices from attacks. This contrary to the findings of Nwosu, Okeke and Ejedafiru (2013) that many libraries do not have genuine antivirus installed on their computer libraries. Also, respondents noted that the computers in the law libraries have genuine programmes and software. However, that the law libraries have smart phones to enhance and enabling ICT facilities such as digital camera scored the lowest mean. This is disturbing considering the fact that no meaningful promotional activities can be successfully embarked upon without ICT facilities. The role of ICT facilities in promotional activities has been underscored by Adebayo (2018).

The study revealed that Internet accessibility and that its connection to the law library is very fast and reliable. This implies that access is provided for both staff and students to enjoy while at the law libraries. This is actually in line with global best practices. However, the finding is at variance with the submission of Olubiyi, Olaniyan and Odiaka (2018) that not all educational facilities have access to fast and high-speed internet. It also negates the assertion by Bankole and

Oludayo that educational institutions in Nigeria lack internet access and that they patronise cybercafé to pay for internet access before they could access this. Also, the study showed that internet bandwidth to the law library is of adequate quantity. This contradicts the finding from a study by Echezona and Ugwuanyi (2010) that most libraries in Nigeria do not have sufficient internet bandwidth. Also, in a study on Internet connectivity and accessibility in University libraries carried out the University of Jos, Nigeria, Abubakar and Diyoshak (2017) noted that Internet access to Nigerian students was slow and that the bandwidth was insufficient. It was further held that such trend could discourage and demoralise users from using the facilities in the libraries with consequent low performance academically. Respondents are in agreement that there is provision for modem in the event of not having sufficient internet access.

The provision of modem outside the internet provided suggests that the internet supply may not be as reliable as previously claimed. The respondents further aver that they use their personal modems to access internet. This is in tandem with the observation of Onwuagboke (2014) that internet use is largely sourced using personal laptops and

modems. This finding goes to further corroborate the assumption that internet access may not be as adequate and reliable as claimed by the respondents. If the internet access were to be reliable as claimed, there would not have been need to make recourse to personal modems. Respondents noted the availability of alternative sources of energy (Such as generators, inverter, Solar, Uninterruptable power supply, Power bank). This is understandable considering the fact that electricity is required in order to power many services rendered in the law library. This is not suppressing considering Dina (2014)'s observation that the Power Holding Company of Nigeria (PHCN), saddled with the responsibility of providing electricity in Nigeria has failed to provide adequate and reliable electricity to consumers including University libraries.

Meanwhile, Ighodaro (2010) averred electric power supply affects the efficacy and competitiveness of every critical economic and social activity which includes university library services. Arubayi (2011) asserted that Delta State University, Abraka spent 13 million naira monthly on one campus running it on generators. Chukwusa (2014) in his study on the need to adopt the use of solar energy, maintained that the advantages of

using solar include: Conversion of light to electricity through solid state device; Cost of maintenance is low; Easy to operate; No supervision is required for a longer period; They are free from pollution; They have longer life; They are more reliable; Because the sun’s energy is free they consume no fuel in their operation; They are easy to fabricate being simplest semiconductor device.

Oghenetega, Umeji and NigeriaObue (2014) recorded that ICT and other electrical equipment are electricity dependent and that lack of regular electricity supply is a major

challenge confronting the ICT advancement of libraries in Nigeria. Meanwhile, the alternative sources of energy is very import to the point that many institutions depend on its use, as though the main source of energy. Respondents agree also that there is electricity supply in their law libraries and that the electricity supply in the law library is from the grid (PHCN). This may be due to the fact that electricity supply for the grid is the cheapest sources of electricity and also environmentally friendly as against the use of generators that could generate both noise and environmental pollutions.

Research question three: what are the types of mobile applications used in university law libraries in South-west, Nigeria during the covid-19 pandemic?

Table 3: Types of mobile applications in university law libraries in South-West, Nigeria

s/n	Statement on types of mobile apps	1	2	3	4	\bar{x}	SD
1	Your law library has social media-enabled mobile apps such as (WhatzApp, Instagram etc.) for promoting library	15 15.5%	20 20.6%	38 39.2%	24 24.7%	2.73	1.01
2	You have dedicated mobile apps in our law library	10 10.3%	45 46.4%	15 15.5%	27 27.8%	2.61	1.01
3	Your law library use other mobile apps for promotion of its services	15 15.5%	35 36.1%	30 30.9%	17 17.5%	2.51	0.96
4	Your law library has hybrid mobile application	20 20.6%	48 49.5%	10 10.3%	19 19.6%	2.29	1.01

5	If yes to 13(a), was it developed by your library	22 22.7%	46 47.4%	11 11.3%	18 18.6%	2.26	1.01
6	Your library has mobile application	17 17.5%	49 50.5%	23 23.7%	8 8.2%	2.23	0.84
7	Your library has native mobile application	14 14.4%	65 67.0%	14 14.4%	4 4.1%	2.08	0.67
Weighted mean = 2.39							

Key: 1 = Strongly Disagree, 2 = Disagree, 3 = Agree, 4 = Strongly Agree

Table 3 reveals that the respondents held the view that their libraries had mobile applications in law libraries. This concurs with the submission of Bowen (2012) that students prefer to spend a lot of time on mobile applications rather than using a web browser. Kolodziej (2015) noted that many of the world leading legal information publishers such as Heinonline and West Law have mobile applications for their services. eMarketer’s (2012) carried out research on the type of applications most college students find interesting, convenient and receive high patronage. The findings from the study showed that most students use mobile applications for communication and social media.

Respondents further revealed that their law libraries use social media-enabled mobile applications such as for promoting their library services. This is agreement with an earlier submission (Lamdan, 2015) that social media over time has become the chief source for news, opinions, and human connections. In the same vein, Intachomphoo *et al* (2016) remarked that law libraries, world over, use social media in several ways to handle the tasks handled by the library. McLaughlin (2025) in a study on the use of social media in eliciting feedback, noted that

academic law libraries now use social media to gather feedback and input from law students and public users for sundry administrative purposes. The finding is in agreement with the study by Bierman & Valentino (2011) state that social media helps law libraries to better engage with users. Jeske et al (2014) describes how law libraries can use social media as a marketing tool to promote upcoming legal database training sessions.

Furthermore, Dority (2013) argued on the role of social media in promoting law

professors and law librarians' research publications, as well as course materials. However, this is contradicted by Melanie Chu and Yvonne Meulemans (2008) who found that students were uncomfortable using social media sites for academic purposes. In a study seeking the views of law students on their preference for the use of social media by their law library. Majority of the respondents, who were law students expressed concern on the use of social media. They categorically raised objection on the use of social media functionalities being implemented in their law library's legal research website, noting that social media platforms should rather be reserved for personal socialisation and not as something to be used in their academic online environments.

Few respondents believed that their law libraries had their own purposefully developed mobile applications and that while the mobile applications were native applications, others were hybrid mobile applications. Niranjana and Chanda (2018) in a study on the use of WhatsApp as a means of Sharing information among LIS professional, identified the use of instant messenger app WhatsApp for delivering information was a veritable tool for information delivery. Olaniyi (2015) stated that Whatsapp in

academic libraries could help to easily send real time messages of individual or group who used library in free of charge and that the services can be provided anytime and anywhere required. He illustrated the process of implementation of Whatsapp in libraries.

An online survey on librarians and users' attitude towards getting WhatsApp as a tool for providing library information services revealed that most of the respondent's attitude towards using WhatsApp in Library is positive (Ansari and Tripathi, 2017). It is also in agreement with the Purkayastha and Chanda (2018) who held the view that WhatsApp can be used by a library to inform the users on the activities of the library, such as upcoming conferences/seminar, Library news, Reprographic services, hyperlinks of e-books, e-journal and other important announcements, notification, and reminder on a particular issue etc. Stephen (2015) in a study on the use of WhatsApp among Library and Information Studies (LIS) professionals discovered that the purpose of using WhatsApp among the LIS professionals reply to the user queries and real time communication between library users and also disseminate the library website/social media/Library Map/OPAC link.

Respondents also agree that the use of Youtube was helpful in achieving promotional services in their libraries. This is in agreement with the findings in the study of

Tella, Okemute and Tella (2018). The respondents also attested to the use of blogs, instagram, twitter, skype, micro blogging, my space, wikis, pinterest and Flicker.

Research question four: What are the Promotional services rendered in university law libraries during covid-19?

Table 4: Promotional services rendered in university law libraries in South-West, Nigeria

s/n	Types of promotional services render	No	Yes
1	Recommendation of library materials	35(36.1%)	62(63.9%)
2	User registration	43(44.3%)	54(55.7%)
3	Interlibrary loan	68(70.1%)	29(29.9%)
4	Selective Dissemination of information	62(63.9%)	35(36.1%)
5	Document delivery	52(53.6%)	45(46.4%)
6	Reference services	44(45.4%)	53(54.6%)
7	Outreach service	69(71.1%)	28(28.9%)
8	Library news	46(47.4%)	51(52.6%)
9	Notification of OPAC additions	57(58.8%)	40(41.2%)
10	Notification of Institutional Repository updates	51(52.6%)	46(47.4%)
11	Notification of new library resources arrivals	41(42.3%)	56(57.7%)
12	Images/photos service	59(60.8%)	38(39.2%)
13	Library orientation	46(47.4%)	51(52.6%)
14	Library education	58(59.8%)	39(40.2%)
15	Leisure/relaxation	69(71.1%)	28(28.9%)
16	Translation	67(69.1%)	30(30.9%)
17	Charging and discharging of library materials	50(51.5%)	47(48.5%)

18	Others	79(81.4%)	18(18.6%)
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Table 4: shows promotional services rendered in university law libraries in South-West, Nigeria.

The study revealed that recommendation of library materials was the major promotional service rendered across the law libraries in South-west, Nigeria. It also revealed that Notification of new library resource arrivals was ranked as the next promotional activity which take place in the law libraries. Respondents engaged in user registration, reference services, circulation of library news, library orientation, charging and discharging of library materials, notification of institutional repository updates, document delivery, notification of OPAC additions, library education, images/photos service, selective dissemination of information, translation, interlibrary loan, outreach service, leisure/relaxation and other service.

Summary and recommendations

Summary of the findings

The findings of this study revealed that:

1. The law libraries in university law libraries in South-west, Nigeria embark in a number of promotional activities with the objective of increasing the patronage and usage of the services rendered in the respective law libraries during covid-19 pandemic.
2. University law libraries in South-west, Nigeria make use of mobile applications for the purpose of promoting services rendered in the law libraries. Among the mobile applications deployed in the law libraries, studies revealed that majority of these mobile applications were social media-enabled applications with WhatsApp and Instagram serving as the two dominant social media mobile applications during covid-19 pandemic.
3. The study revealed further revealed significant relationship between the personal factors (age and years of experience) and the use of mobile applications for the purpose of promoting library services in university law libraries in South-west, Nigeria. This is due to the fact that the staff not minding the age, years of experience and qualification often

perform some tasks that ordinarily should have been reserved for professional librarians, due to constraint of personnel in the law libraries.

4. Against findings in previous reviewed literature, the findings of the study showed that organisational factors did not have much significant effect on the use of mobile applications for the purpose of promoting law library services in South-west, Nigeria during covid-19 pandemic.
5. Relative contribution of personal and organisational factors showed that age as a factor, is significant in promoting the use of mobile applications in university law libraries in South-west, Nigeria. This implies that age could independently predict use of mobile application while gender, status, ICT skills and other factors could not during covid-19 pandemic.

Recommendations

The following are the recommendations flowing from the study:

1. It is recommended that other social media enabled mobile applications, such as facebook with high followers, but not captured in this study, should be embraced by law libraries.
2. There is need to create awareness and build the capacity of staff of university law libraries on the use of mobile apps. for the promotion of the law library services in their respective law libraries. The law library section of the Nigerian Library Association (NLA) and the Council of Legal Education (CLE) can focus on this in their annual workshop for law librarians. In-house training can also be organised while some members of staff can be sponsored for on-the-job training where they can acquire the required basic skills and competencies. Meanwhile, beyond the trainings provided or sponsored by the management of the law library, it is imperative that staff of law libraries put in personal efforts to apply grants, scholarships, fellowships and other sponsored capacity training programmes that

could help them develop their skills without necessarily putting the financial burden of the training on their employers.

3. Authorities of law faculties should appropriate a devoted budgetary allocation for the purpose of managing their mobile applications.
4. There is need for strategic partnerships between the staff of law libraries and perceived relevant stakeholders including vendors, academic staff in other departments such as Library, Archival and Information Studies, Management Information Science, Computer Science, Computer Engineering and other allied departments with interest in Information Technology with the purpose of developing mobile apps for law libraries.
5. With the age showing as a significant personal factor in the use of mobile applications for the purpose of promoting library services in law libraries in South-west, Nigeria, it is recommended that law libraries consider employing young persons with flair for technology, particularly, at the e-library section of the law libraries. This can be extended to other sections, due to the fact that the staff of the law libraries overlap in the discharge of their duties, not minding the unit originally allocated.

Suggestions for further studies

In the light of the findings derived from this study, the following are suggested areas of further research:

1. It is recommended that the study be extended to other types of law libraries across law firms, parliaments, prisons, NGOs and courts.
2. A study scope targeting more states with higher sample size would help to generalise the findings in this area of research. The population should be broader to ensure the generalisation of the result. Selected university law libraries from other geo-political zone of the country can be included
3. Further studies are required to incorporate others factors that could potentially affect the use of mobile application in promoting law library services in South-west, Nigeria. These factors can include motivation, emotional intelligence, job satisfaction etc.

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